

Social Transformation for Water Stewardship
through Scaling Up Citizen Science

Project Deliverable Report

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Executive Summary

This Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) for the OTTERS project sets out the strategy to promote and distribute the project results and outcomes to its stakeholders and end-user groups.

The OTTERS project aims to promote and scale up successful citizen science (CS) initiatives in the marine and freshwater domains.

The key results and outputs of OTTERS will be:

- i) Co-created recommendations for standardisation,
- ii) Guidelines on co-designing large-scale, cross-community, cross-boundary Spring-to-Sea Stewardship CS campaigns,
- iii) Large-scale Spring-to-Sea Stewardship campaigns,
- iv) Three reports summarising an assessment on the effectiveness of citizen science projects in the freshwater and marine environments.

This plan contains the following elements in more detail to formulate the overall strategy for project communication and dissemination:

- Project communication activities aim to inform, engage with, and maintain the interest of a broad audience with frequent communications about the general project activities and results.
- Channels of communication include the project website and social media pages, e-newsletters, a broad spectrum of conferences and events, graphics and other media. Communication activities will be frequent, from the start to the end of the project, and beyond.
- Project dissemination activities are focused on results and outcomes. They cater to specific stakeholders and end-user groups and aim to make the outcomes of the OTTERS project accessible and usable for these groups. Channels for dissemination include scientific publications, reports, guidelines, and factsheets, workshops and focus groups, targeted conferences and events. Dissemination activities will be communicated more widely through the communication channels.
- The plan provides metrics for evaluating the impacts of the communication and dissemination activities, as well as a detailed schedule for its implementation.

1. OTTERS project overview

The OTTERS project aims to promote societal transformation for marine and freshwater stewardship through scaling up citizen science.

OTTERS will support the coordination of EU citizen science initiatives focused on marine and freshwater, aiming to:

- Accelerate the creation and adoption of technical, legal, and ethical standards for citizen science protocols and methods.
- Examine the effectiveness of citizen science in societal transformation towards sustainable aquatic ecosystem stewardship.
- Pilot cross-community, watershed-based Spring-to-Sea Stewardship Campaigns.
- Promote the scaling up of citizen science initiatives through clustering different initiatives, dissemination of the outcomes and results.

The key outcomes will be:

- i) Clustering initiatives and recommending the adoption of new CS standards,
- ii) Preparation and promotion of toolkits and digital applications to aid in monitoring for the requirements of the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD),
- iii) Scaled up collection of real-time recordings,
- iv) Increased knowledge and care for healthy freshwater and marine ecosystems,
- v) Increased understanding on the effectiveness of citizen science,
- vi) Integration and use of guidelines for freshwater and marine stewardship campaigns through EU policies and program,
- vii) Enhanced science-policy dialogue.

1.1 OTTERS objectives

Citizen science is a tool for mass-scale, decentralised knowledge generation that can accelerate research progress and provide valuable insights that might not have been possible with traditional scientific approaches. Citizen science is also a tool to democratise access to research, and to empower individuals to contribute to addressing societal and environmental changes, to foster citizen engagement and stewardship of the natural environment, including the marine and freshwater domains.

To be successful, citizen science initiatives need to standardise methods of collecting data in line with policy, scientific standards, and pre-existing or large-scale/long-term data collection initiatives, as well as overcome institutional and ethical challenges. Data standards will facilitate data exchange through web service protocols, leading to multi-scale interoperability through the effective integration into international environmental databases. Furthermore, it will also increase the use of citizen science generated data by the scientific community, policy and decision makers, as well as other interest groups. Moreover, to achieve the social transformational goals, citizen science initiatives need to be embedded into narratives

and sustained campaigns that aim not only to change minds but also hearts, as well as generate data for research or monitoring purposes. To meet this challenge, **OTTERS** seeks to facilitate EU-funded citizen science initiatives to:

- **Accelerate the co-creation of standards** for citizen science protocols and methods, particularly in marine and freshwater domains. These standards will enhance the scientific rigour, the usability of the data, the policy relevance, increased social acceptability and adoption, and institutional embeddedness of citizen science. This will ultimately contribute to adding a special citizen-generated data layer, including for example real-time recordings of discharges and levels of pollutants and litter for different sites, to be harmonised and made publicly available through EMODnet and hence the European Digital Twin Ocean, and aligned with the Destination Earth initiative of the Digital Europe program;
- **Demonstrate the effective embedding of citizen science in initiatives seeking societal transformation for sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems** to not only generate data and knowledge but also contribute to changing hearts, increasing care and investment for marine and freshwater ecosystems and fostering a sense of agency;
- **Assess the effectiveness of citizen science** for research and innovation, the impact of citizen science campaigns on citizen behaviour and their epistemic relation with marine and freshwater environments, and assess the contribution of specific stakeholders, such as fishing communities, sailors, divers, schools, local associations (cultural, environmental and recreational), etc. All work will be developed, presented and carried out with an inclusive mindset, aiming to achieve a fair representation of society in terms of gender, age, background and other frequent biases;
- Ultimately, **promote scaling up of citizen science initiatives** through clustering of different initiatives, and the communication, and dissemination of the outcomes and results of the above-mentioned objectives, as well as EU-funded initiatives that mobilise and empower citizens to take actions to improve the monitoring of the health of the ocean and freshwater ecosystems and to act against pollution, biodiversity loss and further human impacts. Moreover, to promote digital applications and testing kits enabling citizens to collect data and observations; and lastly, to promote (digital) data collection and participatory research approaches involving citizens for the monitoring and restoration of aquatic ecosystems.

1.2 OTTERS Stakeholders and End-Users

For effective and wide-reaching communication and dissemination, the target groups i.e. the stakeholders and end-users need to be defined a priori. OTTERS will use the term stakeholder to mean any person (or legal entity) with an interest or stake in the project's results and outcomes, or who is directly or indirectly affected by them. The term end-users is used for persons/groups who have an interest in the exploitation of OTTERS results and outcomes. Stakeholders often have different perspectives, priorities, and levels of influence, which can shape their expectations and interactions with the project or organisation. The wider public refers to any other person, entity,

group or organisation who has an interest in any aspect of the OTTERS project or EU Horizon Europe (HE) funding.

Interaction and consultation with end-users, stakeholders and the wider public in the design and development of OTTERS results and outcomes is a key aspect of the project. This approach is fundamental to ensure that the OTTERS project results and outcomes are fit-for-purpose and sustainable after the end of the project. Achieving this requires a robust Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) to reach, engage with and inform stakeholders, to change behaviour, and ultimately ensure the long-term sustainability of the project results and outcomes.

Within the project, a dedicated Communications Working Group (CWG) will map OTTERS results and outcomes to target end-users, stakeholder groups and the wider public.

Communication and dissemination activities will be designed to meet specific goals and target the intended audience to maximise impact and effectiveness.

2. Introduction to the Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP)

Project communication activities aim to inform, engage with, and maintain the interest of as many stakeholders as possible with frequent communications about the project, its activities and results. Communication happens internally between the partners and to the target audiences via tailored channels and tools throughout the project that include the project website and social media pages, e-newsletters, broad-spectrum conferences and events, graphics and media. Communication activities will be frequent (weekly to monthly), begin at the start of the project and be maintained for its duration.

Project dissemination is focused on making project results and outcomes public. Dissemination focuses on specific stakeholders and end-user groups that can use the results. Channels for dissemination include scientific publications and reports, workshops and focus groups, targeted conferences and events, platforms and databases, as well as training activities. Dissemination activities should take place as soon as results are available to maximise the derived knowledge and their impact.

All project partners will participate in communication and dissemination activities through their own channels in their own countries and networks. And they will follow three overarching principles. Communication and dissemination will be:

- Transparent and open, embracing the FAIR principles and the EU guidelines on Open Science, as well as respecting the Privacy and Intellectual Property Rights on data;
- Precise, using accurate language tailored to the target groups;

- Flexible to the changing needs and challenges of the project or its stakeholders, and adaptable to the various stakeholder groups, end users, topics and tools and channels used.

The overarching aim of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) is to achieve maximum impact, visibility and sustainability of the key project results and outcomes through a range of strategic, targeted and engaging communication and dissemination activities, products and channels.

To achieve this aim, the CDP will provide:

- Clear aims and objectives, as well as guiding principles for the CDP;
- Stakeholder analysis to identify the target audiences for Communication and dissemination;
- Targeted key OTTERS message(s) and strapline(s);
- Identified channels of Communication and dissemination for the target audience(s);
- Schedule for implementation;
- Metrics to assess the effectiveness of each Communication and dissemination activity and the overall success in meeting the objectives of the CDP;
- An adaptive and iterative approach to enable responsive action to change requirements or to improve the effectiveness of the communication, dissemination and engagement activities.

This document covers these aims in the following 4 sections below:

- OTTERS Communication Plan
- OTTERS Dissemination Plan
- Metrics for Evaluation
- Schedule for Implementation

3. OTTERS Communication Plan

The OTTERS communication plan identifies the main channels and tools for communication that will be used to inform stakeholders and the wider public about the general project aims, results and outcomes. The first phase of the communication plan already began as the project started and focuses on promoting OTTERS to a broad audience. The plan aims to build a strong community of stakeholders that will bolster the impact of the later dissemination activities.

3.1 Aims and Objectives

The OTTERS communication plan has 3 key aims:

- To communicate the OTTERS project aims, objectives, activities and outcomes;
- To inform, engage with, and maintain the interest of project partners, stakeholders, end- users and the wider society;
- To establish a strong community of stakeholders and potential users to maximise dissemination of key project results and outcomes, with the end goal of improving stewardship of marine and freshwater across the EU and globally.

The communication plan sets out a series of activities and methods to achieve the following key objectives:

- To foster cooperation, collaboration and coordination between OTTERS and related EU projects (published in D6.2);
- To promote and raise awareness of the OTTERS project and its aims and objectives amongst the partners, external stakeholders including potential end-users, as well as the wider public and to maintain their interest using a variety of 1 and 2-way communication channels;
- To inform and update project partners, external stakeholders and end-users, and the wider public on the latest news, events, results and outcomes;
- To further promote outputs from the Dissemination Plan;
- To establish effective internal communication protocols and guidelines to ensure that all communication is delivered in a clear, concise, consistent and timely manner.

3.2 Project Communication Working Group (CWG)

A Project Communications Working Group (CWG) has been established to coordinate communication and dissemination activities throughout the project. The CWG was established and coordinated by the WP5 Leader (Agora Partners) and includes task leaders responsible for communication and stakeholder engagement and WP leaders. Additional project partners and stakeholders are invited to participate as appropriate. The group will meet regularly (at least once per semester) to ensure the CDP is implemented.

3.3 Key Messages

A set of agreed key messages and straplines will ensure that the partners are able to promote the OTTERS project clearly, concisely and consistently. The key message(s) should be agreed upon by the consortium and will help the partners to raise awareness of the project's results and outcomes to targeted end-user groups in a concise, clear and consistent manner. Key messages should use straightforward, easy to understand language to reach as many people as possible. The project will also adapt the key messages to the specific stakeholders that we are addressing.

Key messages are usually around 30 words in length. An initial key message can be derived from the project synopsis as:

“Promoting and scaling up successful citizen science initiatives in the marine and freshwater domains to ensure the sustainability of water ecosystems.”

The CWG will consult with the project executive board and stakeholders to refine the general key message further and produce secondary key messages appropriate for specific environments, geographical regions and different audiences. The primary key message will feature on a suite of initial project communication materials including promotional graphics e.g. flyers, presentations, e-newsletters, blog posts, social media, the project website etc.

3.4 Strapline

A project strapline is shorter than the key message (usually around 6-10 words in length). The main OTTERS project strapline can be derived from the full project title.

“Promoting citizen science for sustainable water ecosystems.”

The CWG will consult with the project executive board and stakeholders to refine the strapline if necessary. The strapline will feature, alone or alongside the defined key messages on a suite of initial project communication materials including promotional graphics e.g. flyers, presentations, e-newsletters, blog and social media posts, the project website etc.

3.5 Acknowledging EU Funding

All communication and dissemination products will acknowledge EU funding as required and set out in the Grant Agreement.

Beneficiaries of EU funding must display the EU flag and funding statement ("Funded by the European Union" or "Co-funded by the European Union") in all their communication and dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major results funded by the grant.

The EU flag and funding statement must be displayed in a way that is easily visible for the public and with sufficient prominence (Figure 1).

EU funding must moreover be acknowledged in all types of public outputs (including patent applications, EU standardisation of results), media contacts and other public statements.

The EU flag and funding statement are available in the Grant Agreement and on the [Europa website](#) (source: [Communicating your project - Acknowledging EU funding](#), accessed 17th

May, 2023).

Figure 1. Example of EU flag and funding statement from the OTTERS project website.

3.6 Channels of Communication

The OTTERS communication strategy will use a combination of 2-way and 1-way communication channels to reach target audiences and their wider networks. Communications activities will be frequent and at the local, national or EU/international level depending on the target audience and the communication method.

The communication activities at the start of the project will build a community of stakeholders to consult, inform and engage with as the OTTERS project progresses. Initially, we aim to build strong networks of stakeholders, end-users and the wider public through the project channels of communication. Establishing effective communication channels and a strong community will provide a vital network to support maximum impact and visibility of the key project outputs and dissemination activities.

The main tools for communication will be the project brand, graphics and website, and the main channels of communication will include social media and media, events, conferences and establishing a stakeholder engagement forum.

The project will also operate a strong internal communication strategy. The OTTERS management structure (D6.1) will link all the project components and maintain regular and transparent communication within the consortium. Regular online meetings (monthly or adjusted according to need) with all consortium members will be organised by the project coordinator to discuss and manage the progress of the project, upcoming events to target, stakeholders and projects to engage, and disseminate project outcomes effectively.

Key methods of internal communication will include regular emails, internal briefs, a shared document drive with all project-related materials, data and information that cannot be communicated on the website, consortium and work package meetings, and the General Assembly meetings held on an annual basis to discuss and update all beneficiaries on the project

progress.

3.6.1 OTTERS Project Website

The project website (<https://otters-eu.aua.am/>) has been designed and developed with the same graphical layout of the communication tools and will be the main point of information on the OTTERS project. It will serve at the same time as an external communication tool and as vital and practical management and communication tool for the project partners. The website will play a central role in the communication and dissemination activities.

The website will be updated frequently (weekly to monthly) with all of the latest news, events, deliverable reports, milestones, tools, publications, graphics, media and other outputs. All new outputs will also be communicated on social media.

Website analytics will be reviewed periodically, and will serve to continually improve website dissemination activities.

3.6.2 Project Brand and Identity

A communications toolbox will be available on the website and will include the official project logos and communication templates, presentation and report templates. The toolbox will provide a suite of project-specific communication resources to partners.

3.6.3 Social Media

The project's social media operates in conjunction with the project's website and blog. Twitter (https://twitter.com/otters_project) and Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/ottersprojecteu/>) are the key public platforms. There will also be a specific thematic/project created on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/otters-project>).

Social media campaigns provide a direct line of communication to related scientific consortia, target industry, policy and education end-user groups and, crucially, their extended networks, as well as the wider public. All new materials, products, news, and events will be broadcast via social media channels. For this strategy to be successful, all partners will contribute. For social media posts, we will be using #OTTERS in conjunction with #MissionOcean and other relevant initiatives to help keep track of posts and reach a wider audience.

The communication team will actively engage with work package leaders and the coordination team to ensure regular external communication of key project activities and outputs. An active community is vital for effective communication, dissemination and engagement.

3.6.4 Blog

The project blog will be integrated into the project website. It will have news and articles published. The numbers of posts are likely to increase as the project progresses and begins to produce its outputs.

Deliverable reports, social media updates, participation in meetings and events as well as dissemination activities will be used to source content for blog posts. All partners are expected to contribute. We will aim to engage and motivate young citizens (students, early career researchers, civil society volunteers, etc.) to produce content for the project blog to give voice to different groups to be heard, as well as increase their interest in the project's outcomes.

Content will be in around 500 words, be suitable for non-technical persons to understand and will be publicly available on the project website. Articles will also be broadcast through social media channels to maximise the audience reached.

3.6.5 Graphics

A set of communication materials will be produced at an early stage of the project. The initial graphics will form part of the communications toolbox updates, and revisions will be provided when necessary during the project. Later graphics will focus on the key project outputs.

All materials will be produced initially in English. Partners can produce translated versions. They will be available for partners to access on the project website/communications toolbox.

3.6.6 E-newsletters

Three (3) e-newsletters will be produced and distributed electronically to internal and external partners. The e-newsletters will include project milestones, highlights, news and next steps. They will be available on the project website and will target internal project partners and external stakeholder groups including relevant research / scientific consortia, industry end-users, policymakers and public user groups. All partners will contribute to a list of stakeholders, collaboration partners and interested entities, and regularly update their contacts for newsletter and other communication purposes in the project's shared document drive.

3.6.7 Conferences, Symposia, Meetings and related Events

OTTERS partners will communicate and raise awareness on the project, engage relationships with other Consortia, and disseminate about project activities and results at relevant high-profile meetings and conferences. The project will be presented by the Coordinator or designated representatives amongst the partners in all major scientific conferences and symposia focusing on marine and freshwater ecosystems during the first/second year of the

project, as well as other relevant EU and citizen science events.

Examples of targeted events include:

- Monitoring and Evaluating the Impact of Citizen Engagement with Mission Ocean & Waters Online Workshop, 16 May, 2023 (attended)
- Joint event for the Missions Ocean and Soil, 22 May, 2023 (attended)
- Sustainable Value Creation Summit, 23 May, 2023 (attended)
- The Digital Ocean Forum, 14-15 June 2023 (attended)
- Diversity of Knowledge, Citizen and Participatory Science, 14 September, 2023
- European Week of Regions and Cities, 9-12 October 2023 (applied)
- BlueMissionBANOS, 14-16 November 2023
- German Forum Citizen Science, 29-30 November, 2023
- ECSA2024 conference, 3-6 April 2024
- UN Ocean Decade Conference, 10-12 April 2024

Forthcoming events will be advertised and partner attendance and activities will be coordinated via the project executive board. Attendance and activities at all events will be recorded on a shared dissemination and communication activities log that will be used for reporting and evaluation purposes. The log will be available to all partners to help track communication and dissemination activities. Partners attending the events will be encouraged to engage with the communications team to produce content suitable for social media, blogs posts and press releases as appropriate. There is also a shared log of potential events and conferences to target, which is kept up to date by all consortium members.

Furthermore, as a CSA project, OTTERS will aim to engage other relevant projects and pursue opportunities for synergies, organising joint events, joint messaging, or promoting relevant projects' events via the OTTERS networks.

General assemblies for all beneficiaries will be held on an annual basis during the project duration for internal communication.

4. OTTERS Dissemination Plan

The OTTERS Dissemination plan will share and promote the main OTTERS project outputs to a range of target audiences. The CWG will collaborate with partners and stakeholders to map project outputs to the key target audiences and to identify effective channels for dissemination. The dissemination activities will use the communication channels, networks and communities established as part of the communication plan to maximise results. The dissemination plan will be implemented later in the project and is expected to increase with project lifetime, as the project begins to produce its outputs.

4.1 Aims and Objectives

The OTTERS Dissemination plan aims to:

- Share and promote OTTERS results and outcomes with target stakeholders, end-users and the wider public.

The dissemination plan sets out a series of activities and methods to achieve the following key objectives:

- To promote how project results and outcomes will improve environmental monitoring, increase awareness and understanding of marine and freshwater systems as well as the contemporary challenges these ecosystems face, and support citizen science projects in the water domain;
- To provide training and capacity building workshops and events that promote uptake and use by end-user groups;
- To present key project results to targeted stakeholders and end-users at specialist symposiums, conferences and exhibitions;
- To present key project results and outcomes to the wider public where appropriate (See Table 1);
- To use the stakeholder engagement forum, communication channels, networks and communities established as part of the communication plan to maximise the success of the projects dissemination activities.

Table 1: Key project results for dissemination.

Key Project Results
<p>Co-created recommendations for citizen science data standardisation</p> <p>OTTERS will provide co-created recommendations for the standardisation of citizen science in marine and freshwater domains to facilitate the integration of the data generated in major EU-funded marine and freshwater data initiatives and platforms (European Marine Observation and Data Network and to the Digital Twin of the Oceans). The standards, protocols, best practices, and data will be in line with FAIR principles, EU WFD and MSFD guidelines, and other legal/ethical frameworks and will be recommended via white papers, policy briefs, factsheets, workshops, the project website and the Citizen Science Resource Hub.</p>
<p>Spring-to-Sea Stewardship CS campaigns</p> <p>OTTERS will co-design transformational, citizen science campaigns for Spring-to-Sea Stewardship and support the clustering of existing CS initiatives under the relevant campaigns.</p> <p>The Spring-to-Sea Stewardship campaigns will include: school children, youth, older people and groups with less representation (for example women and people with disabilities) and stakeholders with a special interest or profession (eg. fishing communities, recreational divers, environmental monitoring hobbyists).</p> <p>Pilots of the campaigns will take place in selected watersheds with ongoing or planned citizen science initiatives. The campaigns will establish networks, offer a roadmap enabling sustainability of continued focus on marine and freshwater ecosystem health.</p> <p>The lessons learnt from these pilots will be summarised into easy-to-follow guidelines and toolkits to designing citizen science projects and similar stewardship campaigns, which will be readily accessible on the Citizen Science Resource Hub, as well as disseminated via the project’s channels and via other relevant European and Mission Ocean projects.</p>
<p>White papers on assessing the effectiveness of CS projects in changing the hearts and minds of citizens towards water stewardship</p> <p>OTTERS will analyse the effectiveness of past and ongoing CS projects in raising awareness of aquatic ecosystems and changing the participants’ behaviour towards these systems. The analysis will result in three (3) white papers and policy briefs offering recommendations on how to positively drive change towards increasing environmental agency and public participation in decision-making.</p>

4.2 Target Audiences

Dissemination products and activities will focus on key stakeholders, including: regulators, scientific community, river-basin management authorities, marine-based industry (including SMEs), policy makers, public authorities, media (conventional and social, including target groups in Facebook), civil society organisations and the general public. The CWG group will work to determine the most effective methods/channels to maximise dissemination results.

A preliminary assessment is shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Tools for engagement for specific target groups

Target audience	Tools to engage
Users in need of knowledge on CS in aquatic environments:	Social media
National park administrators	OTTERS website, OTTERS guidelines
Conservationists/nature conservation societies	Direct outreach
Educators:	Social media, OTTERS website, training and lectures
Science teachers (school level)	OTTERS website, training and lectures
University teachers	Trainings and lectures
naturK, guides	EU.Citizen.Science platform
Citizen science educators	EU.Citizen.Science platform, EU services to disseminate projects (Horizon Dashboard, Cordis, EU innovation radar)
Scientific Community:	Open access publications
Scientific community (e.g. researchers at different career levels, members of higher education institutions/research centres)	Open access publications, Talks at conferences
Natural history museums	Social media
Oceaniums, aquariums, water parks, water museums	OTTERS website Partner newsletters Press releases EU services to disseminate projects (Horizon Dashboard, Cordis, EU innovation radar)
Decision makers:	Open access publications
Policy makers & governance	Social media, OTTERS policy briefs

Water authorities, river basin authorities other regulatory agencies (e.g. fisheries management)	OTTERS website
Public servants/administration	Policy briefs
Spatial planning authorities	Policy briefs
Environmental managers (e.g. coastal or waterway related, conservation, fisheries, aquaculture, tourism)	Press releases
Decision making bodies in academia	EU services to disseminate projects (Horizon Dashboard, Cordis, EU innovation radar)
Water/nature protection agencies	Webinars, workshops, policy briefs
General public:	Talks at dissemination conferences, webinar, social media
Citizens (incl. School children, youth, older people and other less represented groups)	Social media, OTTERS website, Trainings and lectures
Citizen consumers (e.g. of aquatic products like fish, mussels, salt etc.)	Training, lectures, seminars, webinars, (online) courses
Citizen scientists	EUCitizen.Science platform
Interest groups using ecosystem services (e.g. anglers, divers, (water) sporting clubs)	Partner newsletters
Other interested groups	Press releases EU services to disseminate projects (Horizon Dashboard, Cordis, EU innovation radar)
Industry:	Talks at dissemination conferences, webinar, social media
Water-related industry (hydropower companies, waste-water treatment plants, fisheries)	Social media, newsletters
Farmers, dam owners, landowners near water bodies or the sea	OTTERS website Direct outreach, workshops
Consultancies or firms using ecosystem services	Direct outreach

Lobby organisations for this sector	Direct outreach, workshops
Technology innovators:	Social media
Biodiversity informatics experts	OTTERS website
Programmers, open source experts	Open access publications
Data scientists working earth/ocean etc. data and data systems	Open access publications White papers Zenodo Open data repositories and Digital Twins of the Ocean
Decision influencers:	Social media
NGOs, CSOs	OTTERS website Policy briefs Partner newsletters Press releases
Media (journalists, science journalists)	Social media
	OTTERS website
	E-newsletters, partner newsletters
	Press releases
Partner/related projects with synergy	Social media
	OTTERS website
	External communication strategy
	Partner newsletters
	Press releases
	EU services to disseminate projects (Horizon Dashboard, Cordis, EU innovation radar)

4.3 Channels of Dissemination

The OTTERS dissemination plan will use a combination of 2-way and 1-way channels to reach target audiences. Dissemination will be more targeted and less frequent than communication. Dissemination activities will focus on project outputs and results and may be aimed at the local, national or EU/international level depending on the target audience and the dissemination method. Dissemination activities will increase as the project progresses and begins to produce.

The main channels of dissemination will include scientific publications and technical reports, capacity building activities incl. training, graphics and media, targeted conferences, workshops and focus groups.

4.3.1 Scientific Publications and Reports

OTTERS will disseminate the project results through scientific publications following the open access guidelines stated in the GA, and will upload them on the project website. It is expected that most submissions for publication will be concentrated during the last part of the project when many of the results will be available.

4.3.2 Conferences, Symposia, Meetings and Events

OTTERS partners will disseminate and raise awareness about project results at relevant high-profile meetings and conferences. Once new results are available from the OTTERS project they will be presented by any members of the Consortium at national or international conferences, symposia, meetings and workshops, including the workshops organised by WP1, WP2 & WP4, to ensure that the project results will be disseminated to the widest possible audience. It is estimated that each partner will present the project or the results of its work in at least one conference during the 30-month duration of OTTERS. Upcoming events are shared between partners via a continuously updated spreadsheet, the project coordinator and WP-leaders highlight important and relevant conferences and events to be attended and discussions are held during regular project meetings to identify opportunities to attend these events. Thereafter, the partners fill a dissemination log to detail their activities and audiences reached.

4.3.3 Press Releases

Key events, milestones and articles, technical documents and publications will be communicated in the form of press releases. Each partner is required to contribute content for press releases. Content may be at the local, national or EU/international level as appropriate. Press releases will also be posted on the project website and distributed via social media via the OTTERS community established through the implementation of the communication plan.

4.3.4 Factsheets and White papers

Factsheets on standardisation and three white papers on the effectiveness of Citizen Science will be produced to expedite and ease communication of complex information on key findings, recommendations, and results to target audiences in plain language and with clear links to decision choices, helping with making informed decisions. The factsheets and the white papers will be in written format but will also have video or audio corollaries for dissemination. The written formats of the factsheets/ white papers will be published on open platforms such as the project's Zenodo page, the project website, the Citizen Science Resource Hub, and will be distributed to the relevant stakeholders. To enhance the dissemination and impact, these factsheets will be used in conjunction with key meetings and workshops with relevant stakeholders.

4.3.5 Toolkits and guidelines

Lessons learnt from co-designing and piloting three large-scale cross-community, cross-boundary Spring-to-Sea Stewardship CS campaigns will be outlined into guidelines and toolkits that will be easily disseminated via the project's website and social media and made openly available on the CS Resource Hub to be maintained by one of the project partners (European Citizen Science Association) ensuring the sustainability and accessibility of the documents beyond the project's timeline. The produced toolkits and guidelines will also be added to the project's Zenodo page.

4.3.6 Final Conference

A Final Conference will be organised to present the project final results and outcomes, and to directly disseminate the project results to target stakeholder groups. The Conference will be held in M28-29 and will gather all representatives from the partners' countries.

4.3.6 Workshops

Meetings and workshops will be organised throughout the project to involve and co-create with the targeted stakeholders. Three workshops will be organised in WP1 on standardisation of citizen science, 3 workshops will be carried out in the framework of WP2 on the effectiveness of citizen science and workshops as necessary will be organised in WP4 for university faculty on integrating citizen science into their curricula. In addition to the co-creation process on the topics of each work package, the OTTERS partners will collect data and receive feedback on the project's performance from end-users and stakeholders that will be incorporated in the project implementation.

4.3.7 Audiovisual Presentations

An audio-visual presentation in English will be prepared to present the project objectives and results. The presentation will be shown during meetings with target groups and during

participation at events and conferences. It will be available through the project website. The OTTERS Partners will have the option to translate the presentation to national languages.

5. Metrics for Evaluation

The OTTERS communication and dissemination strategy will be evaluated using a variety of metrics. The metrics will be used as a measure of the effectiveness of the communication strategy and channels employed. The strategy will be adjusted as the project progresses to maximise its impact and reach and engage target audiences effectively.

Metrics will include the number of people and types of audiences reached. The EU requires that we collect metrics on outreach and dissemination activities from all partners during each reporting period. For that purpose, the following information will be collected and through the Communication and Dissemination log and by email as part of periodic reporting:

- Number of conferences, events, meetings and workshops organised/attended;
- Number of brochures, posters, flyers, newsletters etc. distributed;
- Number of posts, articles, press releases, papers, tweets and social media updates published;
- Number of people reached measured by session views on websites, followers on social media;
- Number of people attending conferences, meetings, events and workshops;
- Target audience reached for each activity.

Individual key performance indicators for each dissemination activity are listed in Table 3. We will also gather information on the quality of some of our communication activities by requesting feedback from partners, external stakeholder groups, especially those participating in the OTTERS Forum and attending workshops.

5.1 Summary of Communication and Dissemination Activities

Table 3: Summary of communication and dissemination activities

Table 3 provides a summary of the Communication and dissemination activities, target audiences, date/frequency of implementation and the proposed metrics for evaluation

(* C=Communication, D=Dissemination, P/R=Policy/Regulatory, A/S=Advisory/Scientific, B/P=Business/Production, C/C=Citizen/Consumer).

Activity	Type of Activity*		Target Audience**				Communication Type		Date / Frequency	Evaluation Metrics
	C	D	P/R	A/S	B/P	C/C	1-way	2-way		
Website	x		x	x	x	x	x		Monthly to weekly updates	Number of sessions and session time from Google Analytics
Brand Identity	x		x	x	x	x	x		May 2023	Are the communication guidelines being implemented by all partners?
Social media	x		x	x	x	x	x		Monthly posts	Number of shares, likes and new followers
Blog posts	x		x	x	x	x	x		Quarterly posts	Number of shares, likes and views
Graphics (e.g. flyer, poster, banner)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		A first set will be produced in the 1 st semester of the project. Updates and revisions will be provided when necessary,	Number distributed and downloaded

									during the project's lifetime.	
E-newsletters	x		x	x	x	x	x		3 e-newsletters during the project	Number distributed and downloaded
Press releases	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		Annually	Number of likes and shared, number of views
Emails	x		x	x	x	x	x		Ongoing during the project	Monitored for any feedback from partners. Response rate when requested.
Scientific Publications and Reports		x	x	x			x		Aim for 2 peer-reviewed publications and 1 technical report	Number of published papers and reports. Impact factor score (if available).
Capacity building		x		x			x	x	Delivered through the OTTERS MOOCS (First version available by M24)	Feedback from delegates and users using feedback questionnaires. The number of downloads and views of materials.
Conferences, symposia, meetings and industry- related events	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	Aim to attend at least 1 per year	Number attended and presentations / publications delivered, people reached, connections made

Policy briefs / White papers		x	x				x		3 White Papers on the effectiveness of CS, Final version, M28	Number of downloads and views. The number of times distributed.
3 workshops for experts and practitioners on standardisation of protocols and methods for citizen science related to water (T1.3)		x	x	x	x	x		x	5 workshops are scheduled between M2-M24	Feedback from delegates.
3 workshops to discuss insights gained (T2.2)		x	x	x	x	x		x	3 workshops are scheduled between M13-M20	Feedback from delegates.
Workshops for university faculty on integrating citizen science tools into curricula (T4.3)		x	x	x	x	x		x	Workshops are scheduled between M6-M30	Feedback from delegates.
Audio-visual presentation		x	x	x	x	x	x		1 by M12 on an overview of OTTERS and 1 on the MOOC by M25 .	The number of times presented. The number of views. The number of likes and shares.
Final Conference		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	1 will be organised by	Number of delegates.

									M29	
Infographics		x	x	x	x	x	x		At least 1 explaining the concept of OTTERS	Number of views, likes and shares.
MOOC on using guidelines to design and assess CS campaigns			x	x	x	x	x	x	Final version will be released by M28 (D4.2)	To be determined

6. Schedule for Implementation

Table 4 provides the schedule for implementing the communication and dissemination plan. Year 1 provides a detailed monthly plan. Years 2-4 give a more general plan and will be revised as the project progresses to be more detailed. The project started on 1 January 2023 and is due to end on 30 June 2025.

Table 4: M1-M30 Schedule for implementation of the OTTERS Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP)

	Y1												Y2												Y3					
	Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4			Q5			Q6			Q7			Q8			Q9			Q10		
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30
Design, build and launch project website																														
Design project logo and identity																														
Launch project social media accounts																														
Initial project blog posts																														
Set up communication and dissemination log for continuous reporting																														
Set up stakeholder group for the OTTERS forum																														
3 workshops for experts and practitioners on standardisation of protocols and methods for citizen science related to water (T1.3)																														
3 workshops to discuss insights gained (T2.2)																														
Workshops for university faculty on																														

6.1 Collection of Results

It is a requirement of Horizon Europe projects that the activities and results of communications activities are collated and reported.

A spreadsheet to maintain a list of all communication and dissemination activities is available for all partners to contribute to.

6.2 Partner Responsibilities

Communication and dissemination is the responsibility of all partners. All partners will be required to ensure that their activities within the project are recorded, photographed, written and actively communicated.

This is executed through the following process.

1. The partner notifies the communication team on specific events they are attending or organising in advance through filling in the 'Events Sheet' within the shared project drive and providing the necessary information.
2. The communication team can ask that partner for additional text or information to disseminate the event through relevant media channels and the Mission Ocean Platform (when ready).
3. The communication team will instruct the partner(s) on the best way to document the event.
4. The partner(s) are responsible for documenting the event appropriately and sharing the subsequent files with the communication team.
5. The communication team will communicate about the event through all the relevant channels.
6. The partner(s) have to fill in the details of the event in the "OTTERS Dissemination Activities Log" file shared in the project drive.

7. Resources

RI-VIS - Communication Toolkit for Research Infrastructure (2021).

<https://toolkit.ri-vis.eu/community> (Accessed 17th May 2023)

European Commission - Online Manual, Grant Management, Communicating your project.

<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=1867972> (Accessed 17th May 2023)

Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Programme Guide, Version 3.0, 01 April 2023.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf (Accessed 17th May 2023)